

Looking Forward: Bridging Infrastructures for Equitable COVID-19 Testing and Vaccinations

HIGHLIGHTS FROM THE 2021 EVIDENCE ACADEMY DATA PROFILE

The RADx-UP COVID-19 Equity Evidence Academy, to be held Nov. 17 & 18, 2021, will bring people together to better understand the latest information about how COVID-19 testing can help communities. To provide background to this Evidence Academy, RADx-UP has prepared a Data Profile which provides an overview of the different RADx-UP projects across the nation as well as a snapshot of the latest information on how to support COVID-19 testing and vaccinations in communities most impacted by the pandemic. Below are highlights from the Data Profile.

You can also read the full Data Profile [here](#).

COMMUNICATION
TESTING DATA SHARING
PARTNERSHIPS
SCHOOLS POLICIES
PREPAREDNESS

COVID-19 TESTING (& VACCINE) POLICIES, BIG AND SMALL

How can we help develop organizational, local, state, Tribal, and federal policies to promote wide-scale testing and vaccination? The latest research finds that:

- COVID-19 testing remains an important tool to reduce the spread of COVID-19 in communities.
- The policies that direct testing, screening, and vaccination strategies are as important as the technologies.
- To make testing, vaccinations, and contact tracing equitable, community members need multiple ways to get a COVID-19 test and vaccinations—such as at school, at work, at a drive/walk-thru testing site, or through a local mobile clinic.
- Organizations and local, and state, and Tribal governments will need to continually adapt policies to changing science.

COVID-19 SURGE & ROUTINE TESTING

How can communities conduct testing routinely to reduce the spread of COVID-19? The latest research finds that:

PANDEMIC PREPAREDNESS

How can we identify strategies to prevent negative health outcomes from COVID-19 or other public health emergencies? The latest research finds that:

- Federal, Tribal, state, and local governments should have coordinated response strategies to provide COVID-19 guidance to local health leaders, Tribal nations, and public health organizations and officials.
- In the Spring of 2020, a rapid shift to telemedicine helped slow the spread of COVID-19 among healthcare workers and patients. However, telehealth can present challenges to people without access to internet. Health systems and state, Tribal, and local governments should consider how to improve telehealth access for those who need it most.
- Health systems can surge the health workforce by maximizing community health workers; calling upon retired or inactive health workers; giving health professionals the skills they need to take on needed roles; and fast-tracking medical students.
- A national disease surveillance program could help monitor communities for outbreaks or hotspots and help inform policies around social distancing and travel restrictions between areas.

COVID-19 TESTING IN SCHOOLS

Testing in schools is an important issue, with school closures having affected more than 55 million children in the United States. School closures affect children's development and their physical and mental health. The communities most impacted by the pandemic have experienced even more disparities. The latest research finds that:

- Children need to return to in-person school to regain access to important resources such as counseling, meals, social interaction, and after-school care.
- Transmission of COVID-19 in schools is generally low, and there is no correlation between in-school infections and community positivity rate. Safety measures such as testing, masking, and social distancing help to keep transmission low.
- Testing allows schools to determine if other strategies to prevent COVID-19 are working. It also allows schools to catch mild or asymptomatic cases of COVID-19 and prevent further spread.

STRENGTHENING MULTI-SECTOR PARTNERSHIPS

How can we build partnerships to bridge gaps in COVID-19 testing and vaccination capacities? The latest research finds that:

- Public-private partnerships are critical to pandemic preparedness and response, enabling the swift pace of COVID-19 vaccine production, distribution, and uptake.
- Community-engaged research ensures that communities are represented in the scientific process and is essential both for science and social accountability.
- Community-engaged research builds long-term, trusting relationships between researchers and community members.

DATA SHARING EQUITY

How can data sharing across sectors improve community health in the COVID-19 pandemic and beyond? The latest research finds that:

- Data sharing can reveal health disparities, guide the sharing of resources, and improve quality of care and research.
- There is a need for data infrastructure that makes it easier for hospitals, health officials, decision makers, and the public to share complete and consistent data throughout the pandemic and in the future.
- There are many challenges to data sharing, but a few key improvements can advance data quality and ease COVID-19's impact.

ESTABLISHING COMMUNICATIONS FRAMEWORKS

How can we effectively communicate about COVID-19 to multiple audiences? The latest research finds that:

- The evolving nature of the pandemic poses challenges to clear, consistent, accurate communication between stakeholders.
- Community and culturally tailored messages that consider factors such as language, literacy level, and lived experience are essential for communicating with communities that are most impacted by the virus.
- Communicators need to be equipped to correct misinformation and distrust by providing clear and accurate information. 48% of people who live in the United States have been exposed to misinformation about COVID-19.
- Social distancing has moved communications online, but many people remain without access to the internet. Establishing efficient communication frameworks now can improve awareness of testing and vaccination benefits, address community questions and concerns, and strengthen communications in future crises.